

Effect of Electrolytes and Organic Solvents on the Aggregation of some Acid Dyes

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The aggregation of some acid dyes in absence and presence of different percentage of organic solvents (dioxane, ethanol and acetone) and different molarities of salts (NaCl, KNO₃, KCl and KI) has been studied. A simple equilibrium model between a monomer and *n*-mer is assumed to be operative and the absorptivity of the monomer was chosen. The aggregation constant and the aggregation number of C.I. Acid Red 14 and C.I. Acid Red 17 have been calculated using two different methods.

The study of the interactions between dye molecules and other molecular entities is of paramount importance in both industrial processes and medicine. The solvent assisted dyeing has been developed for the industry, and several fundamental discussions and mechanisms of solvent dyeing have been reported¹. The aggregation behaviour of azo dyes having different substituents was studied by means of visible absorption spectra and nuclear magnetic resonance measurements². Through these studies it become apparent that the determination of the extinction coefficient for dye monomer is difficult. This is due to the fact that for dyes with large aggregation constants, the aggregates exist even at the limited dilute concentration where spectroscopic measurements are possible. Different procedures³ were used to calculate simultaneously the aggregation constants. In addition, the aggregation of some dyes such as metal complex dyes in aqueous, non-aqueous and buffer solutions was studied⁴.

Results and Discussion

The aggregation numbers (*n*) of the two acid dyes as well as their aggregation constants (K_n) were determined using two methods^{5,6}.

The electronic absorption spectra of the disulphonic acid dyes, Red 14 and Red 17 were recorded at various concentrations (1.3 to 10.96×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) in absence and presence of 5, 25 and 50% (v/v) ethanol, acetone and dioxane. Different

molarities of salts NaCl, KCl, KI and KNO₃ were added to the dye solutions and the spectra were recorded. On increasing the dye concentration the spectra showed slight shifts. Dyes having localised charges on the sulphonic acid groups possessed broad band spectra which sharpened upon increasing dye concentrations.

Effect of solvents : The effect of different percentage (5, 25 and 50%, v/v) of dioxane, acetone and ethanol on the state of the disulphonic dyes Acid Red 14 and Acid Red 17 was investigated spectrophotometrically. Solutions of dyes in polar organic solvents at room temperature followed Beer's law over an extended concentration range. In water, deviation was observed⁷. Upon increasing the percentage of organic solvents to 50% (v/v), λ_{\max} shifted towards longer wavelength ($\cong 5-10$ nm). The values of λ_{\max} for different percentages of solvents are given in Table 1. The decrease of the association is generally ascribed to the lower polarity of the medium⁸. This effect is attributed to standing capacity of solvents for breaking up hydrogen bonds in water. It is also worth mentioning that the association of organic solvents with dyes⁹ may prevent its self-association. The values of the average aggregation numbers of the disulphonic acid Red dyes are given in Table 2.

Effect of salts : Inorganic salts when present at high molarities can function as disturbing agents¹⁰

TABLE 1—MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY OF C.I. ACID RED 14 AT DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE OF ORGANIC SOLVENT

Dye concn. $\times 10^5$ mol dm^{-3}	Ethanol % (v/v)					
	5%		25%		50%	
	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$
10.96	522	18.43	525	18.50	526	18.75
9.00	522	18.50	525	18.60	526	18.85
7.67	522	18.61	525	18.90	526	19.19
6.00	522	18.66	525	19.55	526	19.66
5.48	522	18.88	527	19.74	527	20.10
4.38	522	19.63	527	20.20	527	21.46
3.28	525	20.06	527	20.73	528	21.52
2.19	525	20.77	526	21.23	530	21.59
1.75	526	20.85	527	21.73	530	21.71
1.30	526	21.23	527	21.53	530	21.92
$\epsilon_m \times 10^3$	21.20		21.50		21.80	
$\epsilon_D \times 10^3$	18.40		18.50		18.75	

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF AVERAGE AGGREGATION NUMBER OF C.I. ACID RED 14 WITH DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Dye concn. $\times 10^5$ mol dm^{-3}	A_{exp}	A_{calc}	ΔA	a	$1-\alpha$	M	n
10.96	2.020	2.270	0.250	0.019 1	0.173 4	2 897.80	5.7
9.00	1.665	1.860	0.195	0.019 1	0.182 1	2 757.36	5.4
7.67	1.428	1.560	0.132	0.019 1	0.225 7	2 226.31	4.4
6.00	1.120	1.220	0.100	0.019 1	0.233 0	2 156.56	4.2
5.48	1.035	1.100	0.065	0.019 1	0.323 2	1 554.70	3.0
25% Ethanol							
10.96	2.028	2.250	0.222	0.020 5	0.207 7	2 419.25	4.8
9.00	1.674	1.850	0.176	0.020 5	0.215 4	2 332.77	4.6
7.67	1.449	1.555	0.106	0.020 5	0.300 7	1 671.03	3.3
6.00	1.173	1.225	0.052	0.020 5	0.482 9	1 040.54	2.0
5.48	1.083	1.105	0.023	0.020 5	0.984 8	510.49	1.0
50% Ethanol							
10.96	2.055	2.235	0.180	0.020 7	0.257 0	1 955.17	3.8
9.00	1.696	1.825	0.129	0.020 7	0.292 8	1 716.12	3.4
7.67	1.472	1.550	0.078	0.020 7	0.411 3	1 221.68	2.4
6.00	1.180	1.230	0.050	0.020 7	0.509 2	986.80	1.9
5.48	1.102	1.120	0.018	0.020 7	1.288	390.12	0.7

which may alter the water structure and bestow the electrostatic composition¹¹ on two dye molecules by the positive atmosphere surrounding the dye ions, thus leading to increased association¹². Both aggregation number and aggregation constant increased by increasing the concentration of the added electrolytes. Different molarities of NaCl, KCl, KNO₃ and KI added to the aqueous dye solutions of the dyes of Red 14 and Red 17, caused clear blue-shifts of 2–12 nm according to the type of the salts. Further, on increasing

the molarities of salts, λ_{max} shifted towards shorter wavelength by 5–15 nm (Table 3). Aliphatic and aromatic molecules or groups present in water are surrounded by a low entropy structure region known as Frank's 'iceberg'¹³ solvation of the nitrogen centers of the dye molecules through hydrogen bonding via the centers of water dipoles may contribute to this region. The hydrophobic association -dissociation phenomena of the dye molecules may energetically arise by the partial melting and forming of this 'iceberg'.

TABLE 3—MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY OF C.I. ACID RED 14 AT DIFFERENT MOLARITIES OF SALT KI

Dye concn. $\times 10^5$ mol dm ⁻³	0.1 M		0.3 M		0.5 M		1.0 M	
	λ_{\max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$						
10.96	515	16.42	514	15.74	512	13.14	510	11.14
9.00	515	16.50	514	15.85	512	13.24	510	11.34
7.67	515	16.75	514	16.16	512	13.49	510	11.73
6.00	515	17.20	514	16.33	512	13.80	510	12.20
5.48	515	17.44	515	16.66	512	14.10	510	12.40
4.38	518	18.26	516	16.89	514	14.38	511	12.78
3.28	518	18.29	516	17.53	514	14.93	511	13.59
2.19	520	18.72	516	17.80	514	15.25	511	14.47
1.75	520	18.8†	516	17.94	514	16.00	511	14.85
1.30	520	19.23	516	18.15	514	16.15	511	15.38
$\epsilon_m \times 10^3$	19.25		18.10		16.25		15.50	
$\epsilon_D \times 10^3$	16.40		15.70		13.10		11.00	

Ion of an added salts can loosen the protective water sheath around the dye molecules, thus destroying the 'iceberg'. Once this protection is disturbed the bare dye molecules associate as a results of the hydrophobic force. The positive environments of cations surrounding the dye anions can also have the power to compel the partly or fully naked dye monomers to unite. A comparatively efficient water structure disrupting salt, can thus function as a more effective dimerising agent. The observed dimerising order is $K^+ > Na^+$. Anionic species may have little or opposite effect due to electrostatic repulsion. Fig. 1 shows the specificity in the effect of cations. Apart from the region of large ionic strength, where Debye-Hückel formula does not hold, $\log k_n$ is almost dependent on the ionic strength (in the region $\sqrt{u} \ll 1$).

The aggregation of dyes in non-aqueous solutions has been studied^{5,6}. The results were used to calculate the aggregation number and the aggregation constant of the dyes. The relationship between $\log C(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)$ and $\log C(\epsilon - \epsilon_n^0)$ for the dye in different percentage of solvents and different molarities of salts was studied. A full description of the method has been reported elsewhere¹⁴. C is the analytical concentration of the dye. The apparent extinction coefficient ϵ at a definite wavelength is expressed by means of ϵ_n and ϵ_m which are extinction coefficients of polymer and monomer respectively, at the same wavelength. From the plots of $\log C_0 \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_m}\right)$ and $\log C_0 \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_n}\right)$ or $\log C_0 \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_m} - \frac{\epsilon_n}{n\epsilon_m}\right)$, the values of n , k_n were

calculated. The results are recorded in Tables 4 and 5.

It is quite clear that the tendency of the dyes to aggregate is inversely proportional to the molecular weight but decreases with the increase in the number of sulphonic groups in the molecule. Also the degree of aggregation increases in presence of salts. Organic solvents help the dye to reach almost the molecular dispersion.

Experimental

Disulphonic acid dyes (C.I. Acid Red 14 and C.I. Acid Red 17) were purified by recrystallising

Fig. 1. The dependence of $\log(K_n)$ on $(-)$ Acid Red 14 and $(- - -)$ Acid Red 17 on the ionic strength, \sqrt{u} : (●) KNO_3 , (○) $NaCl$ and (×) KI .

twice from 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture and dried under vacuum (40°).

TABLE 4—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_n) AGGREGATION NUMBER (n) OF C.I. ACID RED 14 IN DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE OF SOLVENT

Ethanol %	$10^{-2} K_n$		n	
	Ref. 4	Ref. 5	Ref. 4	Ref. 5
5	0.169	0.177	2.2	2.0
25	0.119	0.017	1.9	1.9
50	0.054	0.016	1.7	1.6

TABLE 5—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_n) AND AGGREGATION NUMBER (n) OF C.I. ACID RED IN DIFFERENT MOLARITIES OF SALT KI

KI M	$10^{-2} K_n$		n	
	Ref. 4	Ref. 5	Ref. 4	Ref. 5
0.1	0.926	0.126	2.5	2.08
0.3	0.920	0.177	2.5	2.27
0.5	0.950	0.063	2.9	2.50
1.0	1.009	0.056	3.0	2.67

Dye solutions of different concentrations (1.30 – $10.96 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were prepared in absence and presence of different solvents and salts. The solvent-water mixtures of 5, 35 and 50% (v/v) of dioxane, ethanol and acetone were used. NaCl, KNO_3 , KCl and KI (0.01–1.00 M) were used. All the dye solutions were allowed to stand for 24 h before measuring their spectra at room temperature using a Beckman 25 spectrophotometer. Dye spectra of varying concentrations were recorded in the wavelength range 360–650 nm.

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